

Multi-Objective and Single-Objective Ant Colony Optimization Techniques for Optimal Feature Selection in Data Classification

Ms. Utkarsha Jiwane¹, Prof. R. N. Jugele²

Department of Computer Science, RTMNU University, Nagpur, 440012, India¹

Department of Computer Science, RTMNU University, Nagpur, 440012, India²

utkarshajiwane16@gmail.com¹, rn_jugele@yahoo.com²

Abstract: Feature selection is crucial for improving the performance of data classification tasks by identifying the most informative and relevant features from high-dimensional datasets. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is a metaheuristic technique that is well suited for selecting optimal feature subsets from a finite search space since it has shown strong capability in solving combinatorial optimization problems. Both Single-Objective and Multi-Objective Ant Colony Optimization (MOACO) are efficient for feature selection is shown in this research. The MOACO balances performance and dimensionality reduction by simultaneously optimizing accuracy and minimizing the number of selected features the Single-Objective Ant Colony Optimization (SOACO) aims to maximize classification accuracy. ACO uses discrete decision-making processes that naturally correspond with feature selection requirements in contrast to Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) which is primarily designed for continuous optimization. Experimental evaluation using benchmark datasets and standard metrics demonstrates both ACO approaches achieve competitive accuracy and effective feature reduction offering a flexible and adaptive framework for diverse data driven applications.

Keywords: Feature Selection, Multi-Objective Optimization, Single-Objective Optimization, Combinatorial Optimization, Data Classification, Metaheuristic Algorithms, Swarm Intelligence.

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of high dimensional datasets in domain like bioinformatics, finance and healthcare has made feature selection an essential preprocessing step in data classification. Its goal is to identify the most informative features to enhance model interpretability, lower computing costs and improve classification performance [1]. Large datasets make exhaustive search impractical since selecting an optimal feature subset is an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem. Metaheuristic and Swarm Intelligence (SI) algorithms like PSO, ACO and Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) have drawn a lot of attention for their ability to effectively explore large search space and avoid local optima to overcome this challenge [2]. Although PSO is effective for continuous optimization

additional adaptations are require for its direct application to discrete feature selection. ACO on the other hand is highly suitable for feature subset selection since it is designed for discrete and combinatorial problems. It is inspired by the foraging activity of ants and constructs solutions using pheromone trails and heuristic information [3]. ACO has shown strong performance in problems including TSP, scheduling and high-dimensional feature selection.

This research examines both SOACO and MOACO approaches for optimal feature subset selection. The MOACO simultaneously optimizes accuracy and minimizes the number of selected features whereas the SOACO aims to maximize classification accuracy. This study highlights the effectiveness of both ACO variants in handling combinatorial feature selection problems by formulating suitable objective functions and evaluating

their efficacy on benchmark datasets using standard classification metrics and feature reduction rates.

1.1 Single-Objective ACO

SOACO optimizes a single criterion usually classification accuracy. A binary vector or feature selection path that encodes a subset of candidate features is represented by each ant. Ants select features probabilistically using heuristic information and pheromone levels [4]. The fitness function evaluates each subsets classification accuracy using validation data. After evaluation features in high performing subsets receive more pheromone reinforcement and premature convergence is avoided via evaporation. Although this approach is flexible it may produce unnecessarily large feature subsets and can overfit due to focusing only on accuracy [5].

1.2 Multi-Objective ACO

By extending the conventional ACO with a Pareto dominance strategy MOACO optimizes conflicting goals simultaneously like usually giving a diverse set of Pareto optimal solutions rather than a single result [5]. A vector showing accuracy and subset size is returned by the fitness function after each ant encodes a candidate feature subset. Pareto dominance is used to rank solutions a solution is preferred if it improves at least one objective without worsening another. Evaporation ensures exploration and avoids early stagnation while pheromone updates reinforce features from non dominated solutions [6] [7]. This method offers balanced between dimensionality and accuracy producing models that are easier to understand, more computationally efficient and suitable for real world applications.

This study compares Single-Objective and Multi-Objective ACO for feature selection on benchmark datasets. The analysis evaluates computational efficiency, accuracy and feature reduction. We predict that by managing and balancing between classification performance and model complexity MOACO will provide more and balanced solutions.

2. Literature Review

In Machine Learning (ML) feature subset selection is essential because it improves classification performance while reducing dimensionality. The complexity of modern datasets has increased the demand for nature inspired metaheuristics especially ACO for effective exploitation of

large search spaces but traditional filter, wrapper and embedding methods are still useful.

ML-ACO a hybrid approach proposed by Y. Sun et al. (2020) uses classifiers trained on small instances to guide ACO by predicting the probability that components being part of optimal solutions [8]. In order to enhance feature subset quality across various datasets K. Ghosh et al. (2020) introduced a binary hybrid of ACO and Simulated Annealing that combines global search and local refining to better handle high-dimensional feature selection [9]. ACO-Symmetric uncertainty for streaming medical imaging was proposed by L. Fahad et al. (2020) allowing real time feature selection without retraining [10]. For high-dimensional data W. Ma et al. (2021) presented a two-stage method that combines local refining with global ACO search [11]. Interval Outranking-ACO was proposed by G. Rivera et al. (2022) utilizing outranking relations to guide search toward preferred Pareto front regions [12]. A. Ye et al. (2023) combined ACO with Hybrid Rice Optimization producing strong result in biological applications [13]. Neighborhood discernibility measurements inside ACO were proposed by R. Delamora et al. (2023) which reduce redundancy and increased accuracy [14]. By modeling dynamic redundancy and label dependencies T. Cai et al. (2024) improved ACO performance on multi-label datasets [15]. ACO was also used by K. Niyazova et al. (2024) to optimize feature selection for suspicious transaction identification improving efficiency and accuracy [16]. D. Pathak et al. (2025) offer a comprehensive survey of ACO variants including multi objective extensions discussing challenges like scalability and real time applicability [17].

Despite advancements there are several gaps. The need for scalable frameworks is highlighted by the fact that current Multi-Objective ACO techniques are not well suited for high dimensional or multi-label datasets with dynamically changing redundancy. The majority of ACO based feature selection methods are still batch oriented which restricts their application in streaming environments like fraud detection or health monitoring. Additionally, there is a lack of research on the interpretability of ACO selected features which suggests integrating XAI for sensitive domains. Large-scale, cross domain benchmarking is necessary because many research depend on small or domain specific datasets. Finally limited metaheuristics are the focus of hybrid ACO research which leaves potential for exploring of the Firefly Algorithm, Cuckoo Search or Whale Optimization Algorithm for better performance [18].

3. Methodology

Using ACO to optimize feature subset selection in data classification is a multi stages process. The objective is to identify the optimal feature subset that maximizes classification accuracy while minimizing the number of features selected in order to balance model performance and complexity.

3.1 Problem Definition and Objective

Given a dataset $D = \{X, Y\}$ where $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and each $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the task to find a subset $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$ such that the classification model $M(S)$ gives high accuracy with minimal features.

3.2 Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm for Feature Selection

ACO models feature selection as a probabilistic search inspired by ant foraging.

- **Solution Representation:** Each ant constructs a binary vector $S = (s_1, \dots, s_d)$ where, $s_j = 1$ indicates feature presence.
- **Pheromone & Heuristic:** Each feature has pheromone τ_j and heuristic value η_j .
- **Selection Probability:**

$$S = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_d), s_j \in \{0,1\} \quad (1)$$

where $s_j = 1$ indicates selection of feature j and $s_j = 0$ indicates exclusion as shown in Eq. (1).

Feature Selection Probability

At each step the probability p_j of selecting feature j by an ant is computed by combining pheromone and heuristic values:

$$p_j = \frac{(\tau_j)^\alpha \times (\eta_j)^\beta}{\sum_{k \in \text{unselected}} (\tau_k)^\alpha \times (\eta_k)^\beta} \quad (2)$$

where, α and β control the influence of pheromone and heuristic information as shown in Eq. (2).

Pheromone Update:

After all ants construct their solutions pheromones are updated:

$$\tau_j \leftarrow (1 - \rho)\tau_j + \sum_{\text{ants}} \Delta\tau_j \quad (3)$$

where, ρ is the pheromone evaporation rate and $\Delta\tau_j$ is the pheromone deposited proportional to the fitness of solutions including feature j as shown in Eq. (3).

3.3 Fitness Function for Feature Subset Evaluation

The fitness function evaluates the quality of feature subsets generated by ants balancing classification accuracy and feature subset size.

Single-Objective Fitness Function:

$$f(S) = \text{Accuracy}(S) - \lambda |S| \quad (4)$$

where, $\text{Accuracy}(S)$ is the classification accuracy using features in S , $|S|$ is the number of selected features, λ is a weighting factor penalizing larger subsets as shown in Eq. (4).

Multi-Objective Fitness Function:

The problem can also be formulated as multi-objective:

$$f(S) = \text{Accuracy}(S) - |S| \quad (5)$$

aiming to maximize accuracy and minimize the number of features producing a Pareto optimal set of solutions as shown in Eq. (5) [19][20].

3.4 Dataset and Experiment Setup

To classify channel ranking in 2024 we use a YouTube Channels dataset from Kaggle that has six features. The data is normalized to the range $[0,1]$, categorical attributes are encoded using one-hot or label encoding, and the dataset is divided into training 80% and testing 20% subsets. The ACO parameters such as number of ants, α , β , ρ and number of iterations are initialized.

3.5 Implementation Steps

1) Initialize pheromone levels for all features uniformly.

- 2) Ants construct feature subsets probabilistically based on pheromone and heuristic information.
- 3) Train the classification model using the selected features for each ant's solution and compute accuracy.
- 4) Evaluate the fitness of each feature subset using the defined fitness function.
- 5) Update pheromones based on the quality of feature subsets.
- 6) Repeat Steps 2–5 until convergence or the maximum number of iterations is reached.
- 7) Select the best feature subset from the set of generated solutions.

Objective Formulation

In the Single-Objective ACO the goal is to maximize a fitness function that could be based on:

- Intra-feature correlation
- Feature relevance
- Other statistical measures such as entropy, variance, mutual information etc.

In the multi-objective ACO the algorithm simultaneously optimizes:

- Maximizing the primary fitness score (e.g., based on data quality metrics)
- Minimizing the number of selected features. This ensures a balance between solution quality and dimensionality reduction.

3.6 Performance Evaluation

Performance is evaluated based on:

Classification Accuracy:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Predictions}}$$

Feature Subset Size:

Number of features selected by the ACO algorithm.

Computational Efficiency:

Time taken for optimization and classification.

In this research we propose and compare the performance of Single-Objective ACO and Multi-Objective Ant Colony Optimization MOACO algorithms for feature selection. The objective is to identify an optimal subset of features from a dataset by optimizing one or more criteria.

4. Result and Analysis

In this research both SOACO and MOACO algorithms were implemented for feature selection and their performance was compared with a baseline model trained on all features. For all feature selection and classification.

Table 1: Performance comparison of ACO methods

Method	Accuracy	Selected Features	Execution Time (s)
Single-Objective ACO	0.9825	2 / 6	11.85
Multi-Objective ACO	0.9883	4 / 6	6.96
Baseline (All Features)	0.9766	6 / 6	15.56

accuracy Table 1 compares the performance of SOACO, MOACO and the Baseline for all feature methods. Classification accuracy and the number of features selected from the total number of available features in this case it is 6 and execution time in seconds are among the evaluation criteria.

Fig. 1. Optimization of Single-Objective and Multi-Objective

4.1 Convergence Behavior

The optimization trends of both ACO versions over 50 iterations are shown in Fig. 1 MOACO has balance between accuracy and feature reduction whereas SOACO focuses only on accuracy. Both methods gradually converge after improving faster within the first 20 iterations because MOACO has a balanced search strategy it gets higher accuracy earlier.

4.2 Analysis of Results

- SOACO achieved 98.25% accuracy using only 2 of 6 features outperforming the baseline 97.66%. This demonstrates the importance of metaheuristic feature selection in removing irrelevant or noisy attributes.
- MOACO further improved accuracy to 98.83% with 4 features offering a strong balance between performance and model simplicity through its penalty guided search.
- Execution Time was lower for MOACO 6.96s compared to Single-Objective ACO 11.85s due to more focused exploration and faster convergence.

5. Discussion

The SOACO and MOACO algorithms for feature selection were evaluated in this study that showed their strong ability to improve classification accuracy while reducing dataset dimensionality. The SOACO focused only on maximizing accuracy achieved competitive performance using only 2 of 6 features outperforming the baseline model trained on all features. This shows that several features in the dataset were redundant or irrelevant. Its fast convergence further shows its effectiveness in efficiently exploring the feature space. With only 4 features selection the MOACO gives the best overall results with the highest accuracy of 98.83. Its adaptive penalty mechanism successfully prevented complex feature subsets by balancing accuracy improvement with feature reduction. Because of its guided dual-objective search it also converged faster than the Single-Objective search.

6. Conclusion

The research implemented and evaluated on SOACO and MOACO algorithms for feature selection in classification tasks is compared to the entire feature set both approaches significantly improved classification accuracy while reducing the number of selected features. With only 2 variables the SOACO attained 98.25 accuracy proving that a small set of informative attributes can give strong prediction performance. The MOACO achieved the highest accuracy of 98.83 with 4 features by properly balancing accuracy and model simplicity with its dynamic penalty mechanism. Both approaches outperformed the baseline accuracy of 97.66 highlighting the importance of

feature selection in improving performance and interpretability. The MOACO showed faster and more stable convergence making it a practical choice for real world applications where efficiency and simplicity matters. Overall, the findings demonstrate that ACO based metaheuristics performed well in producing accurate, efficient and simpler models for intelligent decision support systems.

References

- [1] A. Alsaeedi, A. Albukhnefif, D. Shammery and M. Asfoor, "Extended Particle Swarm Optimization (EPSO) for Feature Selection of High Dimensional Biomedical Data," *Neural and Evolutionary Computing*, 2020, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2008.03530.
- [2] P. Priyanka and A. Kumar and B. Vidyapith, "FSHAHA: Feature Selection Using Hybrid Ant Harris Algorithm for IoT Network Security Enhancement," *International Journal of Computer Networks & Communications (IJCNC)*, vol. 17, no. 2, 2025, doi: 10.5121/ijcnc.2025.17107.
- [3] B. Ahadzadeh, M. Abdar, F. Safara, A. Khosravi, M. Menhaj and P. Suganthan, "SFE: A Simple, Fast and Efficient Feature Selection Algorithm for High-Dimensional Data," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol.27, no. 6, pp. 1896-1911, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2023.3238420.
- [4] D. O'Neill, A. Lensen, B. Xue and M. Zhang, "Particle Swarm Optimization for Feature Selection and Weighting in High-Dimensional Clustering," *IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation*, 2018, doi: 10.1109/CEC.2018.8477974.
- [5] Z. Wang, S. Gao, M. Zhou, S. Sato, J. Cheng and J. Wang, "Information-Theory-Based Nondominated Sorting Ant Colony Optimization for Multiobjective Feature Selection in Classification," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 53, no.8, pp. 5276 - 5289, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TCYB.2022.3185554.
- [6] D. Qiao, Y. Wang, J. Pei, W. Bai and X. Wen, "Research on Green Single Machine Scheduling Based on Improved Ant Colony Algorithm," *Measurement and Control*, vol. 55, no. 1-2, 2021, doi: 10.1177/00202940211064243.
- [7] T. Duong, D. Bui and M. D. Phung, "Navigation Variable-based Multi-objective Particle Swarm Optimization for UAV Path Planning with Kinematic Constraints," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 37, pp.5683-5697, 2025, doi: 10.1007/s00521-024-10945-1.
- [8] Y. Sun, S. Wang, Y. Shen, X. Li and T. Andreas et al., "Boosting ant colony optimization via solution prediction and machine learning," vol.143, pp.105769, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cor.2022.105769.
- [9] K. Ghosh, R. Guha, S. Ghosh and S. Bera, "Atom Search Optimization with Simulated Annealing -- a Hybrid

- Metaheuristic Approach for Feature Selection,” *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2005.08642.
- [10] L. Fahad, S. Tahir, W. Shahzad, M. Hassan and M. A. Khan, “Ant Colony Optimization-Based Streaming Feature Selection: An Application to the Medical Image Diagnosis,” *Scientific Programming*, 2020, doi: 10.1155/2020/1064934.
- [11] W. Ma, X. Zhou, H. Zhu, L. Li. and L. Jiao, “A Two-Stage Hybrid Ant Colony Optimization for High-Dimensional Feature Selection,” *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 116, p. 107933, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.patcog.2021.107933.
- [12] G. Rivera, C. A. Coello Coello, L. Cruz-Reyes, E. R. Fernandez, C. Gomez-Santillan and N. Rangel-Valdez, “Preference Incorporation into Many-Objective Optimization: An Outranking-Based Ant Colony Algorithm,” *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 69, p. 101024, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2021.101024.
- [13] A. Ye, B. Li, C. Zhou and M. Wang et al., “High-Dimensional Feature Selection Based on Improved Binary Ant Colony Optimization Combined with Hybrid Rice Optimization Algorithm,” *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, vol. 2023, no. 1, pp. 1-27, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1155/2023/1444938.
- [14] R. Delamora, B. Coelho and J. Sabino, “Improved ACO Rank-Based Algorithm for Use in Selecting Features for Classification Models,” *International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems*, 2023, doi: 10.5220/0011725300003467.
- [15] T. Cai, C. Ye, Z. Ye, Z. Chen, M. Mei, H. Zhang and P. Zhang et al., “Multi-Label Feature Selection Based on Improved Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm with Dynamic Redundancy and Label Dependence,” *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 1157–1175, 2024. doi: 10.32604/cmc.2024.055080.
- [16] K. Niyazova, A. Mukasheva, G. Balbayev and T. Iliev et al., “Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm for Feature Selection in Suspicious Transaction Detection System,” *Engineering Proceedings*, vol. 60, no. 1, 2024, doi: 10.3390/engproc2024060018.
- [17] D. Pathak, A. Mishra, K. Ahlawat and L. Goel, “Ant Colony Optimization: Principles, Variants, and Application Domains – A Survey,” *Smart Computing and Emerging Technologies*, 2025, doi: 10.56155/978-81-975670-0-1-5.
- [18] G. Popoola, G. Fuhnwi, J. Agbaje and K. Fesomade, “A Modified Ant Colony Optimization with KNN for High-Dimensional Data Classification,” *Intelligent Computing*, pp. 262–277, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-62269-4_19.
- [19] M. Hatami, P. Moradi, S. Sulaimany and M. Jalili, “Maximum relevant minimum redundant multi-label feature selection using ant colony optimization,” *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 161, p. 112007, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2025.112007.
- [20] A. Sezgin, M. Ulas and A. Boyaci, “Multi-Objective Feature Selection for Intrusion Detection Systems: A Comparative Analysis of Bio-Inspired Optimization Algorithms,” *Sensor*, vol. 25, no. 19, p. 6099, 2025, doi: 10.3390/s25196099.